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Review Article

Impurity Profiling of Anti-Malarial Drugs

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ABSTRACT

Impurities are the unwanted materials which can interact with the pharmaceutical product and affects the quality of the product or the formulation. According to ICH guidelines, impurity is the part of the drug substance which affects the quality and purity of the active ingredients. Therefore, its identification and control is the major issue in the formulation industries. For the control and the limits of the impurity in the pharmaceutical dosage form, International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) formulated the guidelines for the impurity control and management. In this review, list of the sources of the impurity with their possible causes and effects with their suitable examples are given. Also, the regulatory body and guidelines involved in the detection and identification of the impurity are discussed. The article further discusses about the comprehensive information of the compendial methods and work done on the anti-malarial drugs with their possible impurities along with their structural elucidation and also the detection methods for the determination of impurity.

INTRODUCTION

Impurity:

The “International Council for Harmonisation and Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human use (ICH)” presents the following definitions for impurities and impurity profile in new drug substances. An impurity is “Any component of the new drug substance that is not the chemical entity defined as the new drug

substance. According to ICH Q3A (R) “Impurities in the New Drug Substance.” and ICH Q3B (R) “Impurities in the New Drug Product” a drug substance impurity is “any component of the new drug substance that is not the chemical entity defined as the new drug substance,” and a drug product impurity is “any component of the new drug product that is not the drug substance or an

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excipient in the drug product”.[1-3]Pharmaceutical impurities are those substances which co-exist with the API, or they may develop during synthesis or ageing of both API and formulation. The presence of these impurities even in minor amounts can influence the efficacy and safety of drug. The safety of drug is dependent not only on the toxicological properties of active drug substance itself, but also on impurities that it contains. As safety and quality of pharmaceutical products can be affected by impurities present in APIs, impurity profiling of API has started gaining wider traction. Therefore identification, isolation and quantification of impurities are an important part of drug development and regulatory assessment. In synthetic organic chemistry, it is necessary to submit qualitative and quantitative report on impurities along with API’s so that drug authorities and customer of bulk drug production can use these impurities as a reference standard. Once chemical structure of impurities is reported the reaction conditions or process of manufacturing API can be altered so as to eliminate traceable amount of an impurity to an acceptable level. Impurity profiling gives an account of impurities present in an API/ bulk/ finished products, thus it acts as a quality control tool. The presence of these unwanted chemicals even in small amounts may influence the efficacy and safety of the pharmaceutical products.[4] In a pharmaceutical product, an impurity is first and foremost a quality issue, since it could potentially compromise the efficacy of the drug product.

Secondly, impurities also cause safety concerns. Hence, any impurity present in a drug product must be fully understood, both qualitatively (chemically) and quantitatively, and qualified, if necessary, through toxicological assessment. From a chemical perspective, pharmaceutical impurities are inevitable because no chemical reaction has 100% selectivity, and no chemical compound is “rock” stable. [5-7]

Impurity profile:

Impurity profile is “A description of the identified and unidentified impurities present in a new drug substance”. Impurity profiling is the common name of analytical activities for the detection, identification/structure elucidation and quantitative determination of organic and inorganic impurities as well as residual solvents in bulk drugs and pharmaceutical formulations. [8] In general, according to ICH guidelines on impurities in new drug products, identification of impurities below the 0.1% level is not considered to be necessary unless the potential impurities are expected to be unusually potent or toxic. In all cases, impurities should be qualified. If data are not available to qualify the proposed specification level of an impurity, studies to obtain such data may be needed (when the usual qualification threshold limits given below are exceeded). According to ICH, the maximum daily dose qualification threshold is considered as follows $\leq 2\text{g/day } 0.1\%$ or $1\text{ mg per day intake (whichever is lower)} \geq 2\text{g/day } 0.05\%$. [9]

Table 1: Sources of impurities:

Sr.no	Impurities	Description	Example
A. Organic impurities			
These impurities arise during manufacturing process and/or storage of drug substance.			
It includes:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting material impurities • By-product impurities, • Degradation impurities, 			
Enantiomeric impurities.			

1.	Starting materials or intermediate impurities [10-11]	Starting materials and intermediates blocks used to form the final form of a drug substance. If found in the final product termed as impurities.	In synthesis of Baclofen, p-chlorophenyl glutaric acid present as impurities.
2.	By-product [12-13]	A compound with 100% yield is not possible, there is always the formation of By-product which may interfere in the final product termed as a By-product impurity.	Paracetamol synthesis- Diacetylated Paracetamol is the By-product of Paracetamol
3.	Degradation products [14-15]	Degradation products are formed by decomposition of final product due to improper storage of formulation or ageing.	Degradation of Ibuprofen to 2-(4-formylphenyl) propionic acid
4.	Enantiomeric impurities [16-17]	Chirality of the chemical entity may improve or act as impurities for the product preparation. In case of single Enantiomeric drug, the other form of the drug is considered as the Organic impurities	Levofloxacin and its enantiomeric form S-ofloxacin
<p>B. In-organic impurities</p> <p>These types of impurities are obtained in Bulk drug formulation during manufacturing process and are generally identified and known in nature. It includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reagents, Ligand and Catalysts • Heavy metals impurities • Residual solvent impurities <p>Other materials including Filter aid</p>			
1	Reagents, Ligand and Catalysts [18-19]	Reagents, ligand and catalysts during the manufacturing process may act as impurities in the formulation. Presence of any of these material act as impurity for the finished product and may be identified during the identification of the impurity	Raney Ni is used as a catalyst reduction reaction of Linezolid, and lead to the formation of impurities along with Linezolid.
2	Heavy metals [20]	Water is the most abundant solvent used in the formulation of any product, but unfortunately water act as the major source of heavy metals which interfere in the formulation and may lead to hydrolysis of the drug	Ag, Cd, Na. Mn and Mg are some of the general heavy metals present in the water.
3	Filter aids [18]	Filtering aids are used in many synthesis of the drug, which may act as the source of impurities for the drug during the filtration.	Fibers present in the filter, centrifuge bags, activated charcoal and black particles etc, act as the impurities.
<p>C. Residual Solvents [21]</p> <p>These are organic or inorganic liquids which are generally used in various manufacturing processes. Some liquids exhibit toxic behaviour so, they need to be eliminated. Classified as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Class 1 Solvents • Class 2 Solvents 			

Class 3 Solvents			
1.	Class 1 Solvents	Solvents to be avoided because of its high toxicity	Benzene, Carbon tetrachloride, 1,1 Dichloroethane, 1,2 Dichloroethane etc.
2.	Class 2 Solvents	Solvents to be limited	Acetonitrile, Chloroform, Pyridine, Toluene etc.
3.	Class 3 Solvents	Solvents with low toxic potential therefore it can be used	Acetic acid, Ethanol, Butanol, Acetone etc.
D. Synthesis related impurities ^[22]			
<p>An impurity formed during synthesis of drug, even in minor amounts, could ultimately be present in final product and therefore, synthesis related impurities require careful monitoring at every step, to minimize amount of impurity that can formed.</p> <p>e.g. During the synthesis of the Hydroxy amide lactam-related impurity obtained along with the synthesis.</p>			
E. Formulation related impurities ^[14]			
<p>This involves the impurities produced during the formulation of product. Numerous impurities arise due to excipients, solvents, etc used in the formulation of the product such as solutions, tablets, capsules, semi-solids, aerosols etc.</p> <p>Classified as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Method related impurity <p>Dosage form related impurity</p>			
1	Method related impurity ^[23]	<p>This involves the formation of the impurity in the formulation during the process and method followed for the formulation of product and this factor also affect the quality of the product.</p> <p>It involves changes in pH, solubility, method of sterilization, time of mixing and drying etc.</p>	Diclofenac sodium – impurity formation due to changes in the pH and sterilization conditions.
2	Dosage form related impurity ^[24]	<p>Degradation of the dosage form, due to changes in the physico-chemical conditions such as pH or light sensitive drug, moisture sensitive compound etc.</p> <p>This condition may cause the recall of the product from the market.</p>	Moisture absorption in the lactose, Imipramine hydrochloride precipitation, Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose cause discolouration.
F. Environmental related			
<p>The factors affected due to changes in the environmental condition of the formulation.</p> <p>It involves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temperature changes • Light/ UV light <p>Humidity</p>			
	Temperature changes ^[25]	<p>Most of the APIs and the formulation prepared form the APIs are heat sensitive, and therefore due to changes in the temperature adversely effects the formulation and leads to degradation.</p>	Heat sensitive compounds Vitamins: - Folic acids, Pantothenic acid, Cyanocobalamine, Thiamine.

	Light/ UV light ^[26]	Many pharmaceutical products degrade as the exposure of some type and amount of light and therefore formulation must be protected from the overexposure	Ergometrine gets completely degrade when exposed to direct sunlight for 42 hours.
	Humidity ^[26]	It is the major destabilizing factor for hygroscopic compounds	Aspirin, Ranitidine and other hygroscopic drugs gets degrades when comes to contact with humidity.
G. Functional group related			
<p>The changes in the functional group of the compound may leads to degradation. Changes of the functional group due to any of these- Oxidation, Reduction, Hydrolysis, etc</p> <p>It involves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrolysis • Photolytic cleavage • Decarboxylation • Oxidative degradation • Packaging material <p>Ageing</p>			
	Hydrolysis ^[27]	Some drugs are prone to get hydrolysed when comes in contact with water of factors influence hydrolysis.	Ester type formulation, Barbitol, chloramphenicol, etc.
	Photolytic cleavage ^[28]	It defines as the photo oxidation of the product due to the over or exposure of the pharmaceutical product which are generally light sensitive.	Nifedipine, Riboflavin, Phenothiazine etc.
	Decarboxylation ^[29]	This defines as the removal or loosing of the carbon dioxide from the carboxyl group.	p-amino salicylic acid, Rufloxacin, etc.
	Packaging material ^[29]	Impurities are generated are general due to packaging material because the first line of the contact with the product is the primary packaging material, which may produce impurity in the product and formulated formulation by the several process such as leaching, leaking etc	Impurities produced by the packaging material are polypropylene, zinc stearate, styrene, NO ₂ , SiO ₂ , MgO etc.
	Ageing ^[30]	As the time passes in the formulation, its inter-reaction leads to the formation of the impurities. Due to interaction of APIs and excipients added for the formulation.	Vitamin B complex injection, Thiamine etc.

Impurity detection methods:

To evaluate the impurity in the synthesis of APIs, formulation of the product or in the finished

product several methods are available to evaluate it includes:

- Isolation methods
- Separation methods

- Characterization methods

Table 2: Impurity detection methods

Sr.no	Method	Description	Example
A. Isolation methods ^[31-32]			
<p>Estimation of the impurity in the synthetic or the bulk formulation are made on the basis of assumptions related to the characteristics of the product formulated as well as the raw material used for the formulation. Based on it next step is to isolate and monitor the impurity during the actual synthetic process. It involves following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liquid-solid extraction Liquid-liquid extraction Soxhlet extraction <p>Gas chromatography</p>			
1.	Liquid-solid extraction	A solvent used in this type of extraction is generally able to dissolve the impurity of interest. Generally, this type of properties are found in the organic solvents and therefore, most of the time organic solvents are selected based on the properties.	Toluene, methanol cyclohexane etc.
2.	Liquid-liquid extraction	It involves extraction of one liquid with another ones. In which one is aqueous, and the other is organic which are mutually immiscible.	Water and oil
3.	Soxhlet extraction	This method is generally used for the natural compounds extraction. It utilizes small amount of solvent and main advantage of this method is solvent can be recycled for the usage of other process or extraction.	Isolation of curcumin from rhizomes of turmeric.
4.	Gas chromatography	It is useful for the isolation of the volatile impurity or compound that can be volatilized, formed during the synthetic process of the formulation.	Synthesis of Doxorubicin hydrochloride- acetone and methanol found to be as impurity.
B. Separation methods ^[33]			
<p>After the process, the next step is to separate the mixture of impurity compounds into individual ones</p> <p>It involves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thin layer chromatography Column chromatography High pressure liquid chromatography <p>Capillary electrophoresis</p>			
Thin layer chromatography	Valuable and cheapest technique for the separation of the compounds and works on the principle of	Dehydro-apixaben impurity detected by the TLC	Thin layer chromatography

	adsorption. Detection by UV.		
Column chromatography	This method is used for the quantitative separation or analysis of the impurity ranging from the milligram (mg) to kilogram (K g). UV-spectrometry is used for the detection.	Mirabegron impurity	Column chromatography
High pressure liquid chromatography	Principle is based on the separation. In the majority of the cases there is the use of RP-HPLC condition and detection by UV method.	L-Asparaginase	High pressure liquid chromatography
Capillary electrophoresis	This plays an important role in solving the problem of the toxic impurity batches based on the separation principle and also detected by UV-Spectrometry.	Heparin impurity, sulphate impurity	Capillary electrophoresis
C. Characterization methods ^[34] Highly sophisticated instruments are used for the monitoring and quantification of the impurity even in the minor amount Involves: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NMR • MS • GC-MS 			
NMR	Provides the information regarding the molecular structure and the stereochemistry of the impurity and multi-compounds can be easily analysed.	Benzyl (4-morpholino phenyl) carbamate, dehydro-apaxiben etc.	NMR
MS	This is the most accurate technique for the determination of the molecular mass and elemental composition of the found impurity. Also used for monitoring, characterization and quantification of the drug related substance in API.	Des-fluoro impurities-Sertalin and Linezolid	MS

GC-MS	For the identification of the different substance within a sample, GC can be coupled with MS to provide better information. In this method GC provides volatility of the compound and MS provides structural information	Ethanol, hexane, benzene etc.	GC-MS
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Regulatory guidelines for determination of impurities:

Monitoring and controlling of impurities imply different things. Therefore, simple terminology should be used to address questions related to impurities. The United States food and drug administration (US-FDA) has endorsed the guidelines prepared by International Conference on Harmonization (ICH). The ICH guidelines for impurities were developed with joint efforts of various regulators such as European Union (EU), Japan and United States and they help in ensuring consistent requirement of data that should be submitted to various regulatory agencies. The guidelines are not only to aid the sponsors of New Drug Application (NDA) or Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA) with information that should be submitted along with their applications, but also assists FDA reviewers and field investigators in consistent implementation and interpretation of regulations.

The various regulatory guidelines are as follows:

- ICH guidelines “Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products”- Q1A.

- ICH Guidelines “Impurities in New Drug Substances”- Q3A.
 - ICH Guidelines “Impurities in New Drug Products”- Q3B.
 - ICH Guidelines “Impurities: Guidelines for Residual Solvents”- Q3C.
 - US-FDA Guidelines “NDAs- Impurities in New Drug Substances”.
 - US-FDA Guidelines “ANDAs- Impurities in New Drug Substances”.
 - Australian Regulatory Guideline for Prescription of Medicines, Therapeutic Governance Authority (TGA), Australia. [35-37]
- Impurity profiling of Anti-Malarial drugs:
Malaria is the most common and important parasitic disease in humans. About three billion people in the world live at risk of contracting malaria.[1] In humans, malaria is caused by one of the five species of the genus Plasmodium: P. vivax, P. malarie, P. falciparum, P. ovale and P. knowlesi.[2] There are several drugs and their formulations available for the treatment of Malaria.

Table 3: Classification of anti-Malarial drugs:

CLASSIFICATION	DRUG
4-Aminoquinolines	Chloroquine, Amodiaquine, Piperaquine
Quinoline-methanol	Mefloquine
Cinchona alkaloids	Quinine, Quinidine
Biguanides	Proguanil
Diaminopyrimidine	Pyrimethamine
8-Aminoquinolines	Primaquine
Sulfonamide	Sulfadoxine, Sulfamethopyrazine

Antibiotics	Doxycycline, Clindamycin
Sesquiterpine-lactone	Artesunate, Artemether, Arteether, Arterolane
Amino-alcohol	Lumefantrine
Naphthoquinone	Atovaquone

Table 4: Impurity profiling of compendial anti-malarial drugs:

Sr. no	Drug	Impurities	Method
1.	Chloroquine ^[38]	Heavy metals, water	TLC Stationary phase: Silica gel G254 Mobile phase: chloroform: cyclohexane: diethylamine (50:40:10) Injection volume: 5 µL
2.	Amodiaquine ^[39]	Sulphated ash	TLC Stationary phase: silica gel G254 Mobile phase: chloroform: Ethanol (90:10) Injection volume: 10 µL
3.	Artesunate ^[40]	Impurity A, Impurity B, Impurity C	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: Buffer solution pH 3 made with potassium dihydrogen phosphate: acetonitrile (56:44) Flow rate: 1mL/min Injection volume: 20µL
4.	Artemether ^[41]	Sulphated ash, phosphorus pentoxide	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: acetonitrile: water (62:38) Flow rate: 1.5 mL/min Injection volume: 20µL
5.	Doxycycline ^[42]	Heavy metals, sulfonated ash, water	TLC Stationary phase: Silica gel H Mobile phase: Dichloromethane: methanol: water (59:35:6) Flow rate: 1 mL/min Injection volume: 20µL
6.	Clindamycin ^[43]	Impurity A, Impurity B	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: 2-propanol: ammonium acetate: ethyl acetate (19:28:43) Flow rate: 1 mL/min Injection volume: 20µL
7.	Mefloquine ^[44]	Heavy metals, sulfonated ash, water	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: Methanol: sodium hydrogen sulphate: acetonitrile (20:40:40)

			Flow rate: 0.8 mL/min Injection volume: 20 µL
8.	Quinidine ^[45]	Impurity A, Impurity B, Impurity C, Impurity D	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: Methanol: sodium hydrogen sulphate: acetonitrile (20:40:40) Flow rate: 1.5 mL/min Injection volume: 10 µL
9.	Quinine ^[46]	Di-hydroquinidine, Di-hydroquinone, quinidine	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: Methanol: sodium hydrogen sulphate: acetonitrile (20:40:40) Flow rate: 1 mL/min Injection volume: 5 µL
10.	Proguanil ^[47]	Impurity A, Impurity B, Impurity C, Impurity D	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: Heptane-sulfonate: water: acetonitrile Flow rate: 1 mL/min Injection volume: 20 µL
11.	Pyrimethamine ^[48]	Sulphates, sulphonated ash	TLC Stationary phase: silica gel G254 Mobile phase: Toluene: GAA:1-propanol: chloroform (76:12:8:4) Flow rate: 1 mL/min Injection volume: 20 µL
12.	Primaquine ^[49]	Impurity A, Impurity B	TLC Stationary phase: silica gel F254 Mobile phase: Methanol: chloroform (40:60) Flow rate: 3 mL/min Injection volume: 20 µL
13.	Arteether ^[50]	Impurity A, Impurity B, Impurity C, sulphated ash	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: water (70:30) Flow rate: 1.5 mL/min Injection volume: 20 µL
14.	Arterolane [51]	Melic acid, heavy metals, sulphated ash, water	HPLC Stationary phase: Stainless steel column packed with octadecylsilane bonded to porous silica Mobile phase: Potassium dihydrogen phosphate: triethylamine: pH adjusted to 4.5 with ortho phosphoric acid Flow rate: 1 mL/min

			Injection volume: 25 µL
15.	Sulfadoxine [52]	Impurity A,	TLC Stationary phase: silica gel F254 R Mobile phase: ammonia: Methanol (4:96)
16.	Lumefantrine [53]	Desbutyl-lumefantrine ((2)-2-(Butylamino)-1-(2,2-dichloro-5-(4-chlorobenzylidene)- fluore-4-ethanol)	LC Stationary phase: Packing L1 column Flow rate: 2.5 mL/min Injection volume: 2.5µL Run time: 20 min Column temperature: 50-35°C
17.	Atovaquone [54]	2-(sun-4-(4-chlorophenyl) cydoheryl)-1-e-1/F-inden 3-carboxylic acid,	HPLC Stationary phase: end-capped octadecyl silica gel Mobile phase: phosphoric acid: methanol: water: acetonitrile (0.5:17.5:30:52.5) Flow rate: 2.5 mL/min Injection volume: 20 µL

Table 5: Work done on impurity profiling of the anti-malarial drugs:

1. Chloroquine ^[55-56]	
<p>Figure 1: Chloroquine</p>	
Impurities	Method
<p>Figure 2: PD1</p>	<p>UHPLC-UV-MS/MS Stationary phase: C18 Mobile phase: TEA: Methanol (25:75) Flow rate: 1mL/min Injection volume: 10µL</p>
<p>Figure 3: PD2</p>	
<p>Figure 4: CQ1</p>	<p>LC/IT/MS, LC/TOF/MS, NMR Stationary phase: C18 column Mobile phase: TEA: acetonitrile: isopropyl alcohol (87:12:1) Flow rate: 1.2 mL/min Injection volume: 1 µL</p>
<p>Figure 5: CQ2</p>	

2. Amodiaquine [57]	
<p>Figure 6: Amodiaquine</p>	
Impurities	Method
<p>Figure 9: 4- [(7- chloroquinolin-4-yl) amino]-2-(diethylaminomethyl)-N1 - oxy] phenol.</p>	<p>MS/MS, GC/MS, NMR, LC/MS Stationary phase: C18 column Mobile phase: 0.02M ammonium acetate:0.01% TEA: Acetonitrile (12:18:70) Flow rate: 0.7 mL/min Injection volume: 1 µL</p>
3. Piperaquine [58-59]	
<p>Figure 10: Piperaquine</p>	
Impurities	Method
	<p>LC/MS/MS, NMR Stationary phase: C18 column Mobile phase: 0.02M disodium hydrogenphosphate:0.01% TEA: Acetonitrile (28:2:70) Flow rate: 0.7 mL/min</p>

Figure 11: 7-chloro-4- piperazinyl quinoline, 1-chloro-3-(7- chloro-4-quinolyl-4-piperazinyl) propane.

Figure 12: 1,4-bis- (4,7-dichloroquinoline) piperazine.

Figure 13: N-propyl piperazine moiety

Figure 14: 7-chloro-4-piperazinyl quinoline, 1-chloro-3-(7-chloro-4-quinolyl-4-piperazinyl) propane.

Figure 15: 1-(1-5-chloro-4-quinolyl-4-piperazinyl)-3-(1-7- chloro-4-quinolyl-4-piperazinyl) propane.

Figure 16: 1,4-bis-(4,7- dichloro-quinoline) piperazine

Injection volume: 20 μ L

HPLC-UV, TOF-MS, ESI-MS NMR
Stationary phase: C18 analytical column
Mobile phase: 0.1% ammonium phosphate:
 ammonium acetate solution (40:60)
Flow rate: 1 mL/min
Injection volume: 20 μ L

4. Mefloquine^[60]

Figure 17: Mefloquine

Impurities

Figure 18: Piperidyl

Method

MS
Stationary phase: silica.GF
Mobile phase: toluene: ethanol: NH₄OH (34:15:1)
Flow rate: 2 mL/min

5. Quinine & Quinidine^[61]

Figure 19: Quinine & Quinidine

Impurities

Figure 20: Dihydro-quinine

Method

HPLC-Fluorescence
Stationary phase: ultra-sphere C18 reversed-phase column
Mobile phase: acetonitrile: water: TEA (11:88:1)
Flow rate: 1 mL/min
Retention time: 30 min

6. Proguanil^[62]

Figure 22: Proguanil

Impurities

Figure 23: Isopropyl biguanide

Figure 24: 4-chloroaniline

Method

ESI-MS, TSI-MS, APPI-MS, APCI-MS, CE/UV,
 CE/MS, LC/MSD XCT, CE/ESI-MS, CE/APPI-MS,
 CE/APCI-MS
 LC/MSD
Stationary phase: C18 analytical column
Mobile phase: acetonitrile: methanol: TEA
 (40:60:0.2)
Flow rate: 2 mL/min
Injection volume: 20 µL

Figure 25: Proguanil bis-compound

7. Pyrimethamine ^[63]

Figure 26: Pyrimethamine

Impurities

Method

Figure 27: Impurity A

Figure 28: Impurity B

Figure 29: Impurity C

LC/MSD
Stationary phase: Europher-II C₁₈H column
Mobile phase: potassium dihydrogen phosphate:
 ortho phosphoric acid (15:85)
Flow rate: 1-2 mL/min
Injection volume: 20 µL

<p>Figure 30: Impurity D</p>	
<p>8. Primaquine ^[64-66]</p> <p>Figure 31: Primaquine</p>	
<p>Impurities</p>	<p>Method</p>
<p>Figure 32: Quinocide</p>	<p>CAPILLARY ZONE ELECTROPHORESIS Uncoated fused-silica capillary 1M NaOH, methanol pH 2.5-4.5 R_s 3.5-3.8</p>
<p>Figure 35: 4-bromo-1-phthalamido pentane</p>	<p>LC-ESI-MS/MS, GC-EI-MS, GC-MS Stationary phase: DB5 column Carrier gas: Helium Flow rate: 1.9 mL/min</p>

<p>Figure 37: 8-nitro-6-methoxy quinoline</p>	<p>UPLC</p> <p>Stationary phase: Kromasil C18 column Mobile phase: Acetonitrile: Trifluoroacetic acid (25:75) Flow rate: 1 mL/min Injection volume: 10 µL</p>
<p align="center">9. Sulfadoxine ^[67]</p> <p align="center">Figure 38: Sulfadoxine</p>	
<p align="center">Impurities</p>	<p align="center">Method</p>
<p>IMP IX, IMP XI</p>	<p>LC-MS</p> <p>Stationary phase: Sunfire C18 column Mobile phase: CH₃COOO:CH₃CN Flow rate: 1 mL/min</p>
<p align="center">10. Sulfamethopyrazine ^[68]</p> <p align="center">Figure 39: Sulfamethopyrazine</p>	
<p align="center">Impurities</p>	<p align="center">Method</p>
<p>Figure 40: 4-amino-N-(6-hydroxypyrazin-2-yl) benzene sulfonamide</p>	<p>LC/MS/MS, HPLC, NMR, IR</p> <p>Stationary phase: Unisphere C18 column Mobile phase: Perchloric acid (70%): acetonitrile (85:15) Flow rate: 0.8 mL/min Injection volume: 20 µL</p>

Figure 41: 4-amino-N-(pyrazin-2-yl) benzene sulfonamide

Figure 42: 4-amino-N-(6-methoxypyrazin-2-yl) benzene sulfonamide

11. Doxycycline ^[69]

Figure 43: Doxycycline

Impurities

Method

Figure 44: Metacycline (MTC)

Figure 45: 6-epidoxycycline (EDOX)

HPLC-DAD, LC-ESI-MS
Stationary phase: Synergi polar-RP column
Mobile phase: Oxalic acid: acetonitrile (82:12)
Flow rate: 0.3 mL/min
Injection volume: 20 µL

12. Clindamycin ^[70-71]

Figure 46: Clindamycin

Impurities	Method																																								
<p>Figure 48: Impurity 2</p>	<p>MS, NMR Plate: 5 µL</p>																																								
<table border="1" data-bbox="316 976 673 1144"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>R₁</th> <th>R₂</th> <th>R₃</th> <th>R₄</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1 Lincomycin</td> <td>CH₂CH₂CH₂</td> <td>HO-</td> <td>H-</td> <td>HO-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 7-Epilincosamin-2-phosphate</td> <td>CH₂CH₂CH₂</td> <td>H-</td> <td>HO-</td> <td>H₂O₂PO-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3 Lincomycin-2-phosphate</td> <td>CH₂CH₂CH₂</td> <td>HO-</td> <td>H-</td> <td>H₂O₂PO-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4 Clindamycin B</td> <td>CH₂CH₂</td> <td>H-</td> <td>Cl-</td> <td>HO-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5 Clindamycin B-2-phosphate</td> <td>CH₂CH₂</td> <td>H-</td> <td>Cl-</td> <td>H₂O₂PO-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6 Clindamycin</td> <td>CH₂CH₂CH₂</td> <td>H-</td> <td>Cl-</td> <td>HO-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7 Clindamycin-2-phosphate</td> <td>CH₂CH₂CH₂</td> <td>H-</td> <td>Cl-</td> <td>H₂O₂PO-</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Figure 49: Lincomycin, 7-epilincosamin-2-phosphate, lincomycin-2-phosphate, clindamycin B, clindamycin B-2-phosphate.</p>		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	1 Lincomycin	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	HO-	H-	HO-	2 7-Epilincosamin-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	HO-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-	3 Lincomycin-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	HO-	H-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-	4 Clindamycin B	CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	HO-	5 Clindamycin B-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-	6 Clindamycin	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	HO-	7 Clindamycin-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-	<p>HPLC/ESI-MS/MS Stationary phase: RP silica column sepax HP-C18 Mobile phase: acetonitrile: tetrahydrofuran: water: formic acid (25:2.85:72.15:0.2) Flow rate: 0.80 mL/min Injection volume: 10 µL</p>
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄																																					
1 Lincomycin	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	HO-	H-	HO-																																					
2 7-Epilincosamin-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	HO-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-																																					
3 Lincomycin-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	HO-	H-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-																																					
4 Clindamycin B	CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	HO-																																					
5 Clindamycin B-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-																																					
6 Clindamycin	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	HO-																																					
7 Clindamycin-2-phosphate	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	H-	Cl-	H ₂ O ₂ PO-																																					
<p>13. Artesunate ^[72]</p> <p>Figure 50: Artesunate</p>	<p>Method</p>																																								
<p>Impurities</p>	<p>Method</p>																																								

<p>Figure 53: Impurity C</p>	<p>HPLC Stationary phase: BEH C18 Mobile phase: water: ethanol (95:5) Flow rate: 0.4 mL/min Injection volume: 10 µL</p>
<p>14. Artemether ^[73]</p> <p>Figure 54: Artemether</p>	
<p>Impurities</p> <p>Figure 55: Diketo-aldehyde (DKA)</p>	<p>Method</p> <p>LC-UV/MS Stationary phase: Prevail organic acid column Mobile phase: phosphate buffer pH 2.5: acetonitrile (30:75) Flow rate: 1.5 mL/min</p>

Figure 56: Dihydro artemisinin (DHA)

Figure 57: α -artemether

Figure 58: 9,10-anhydroartemisinin (AHA)

Figure 59: Artemisinin

15. Lumefantrine ^[74-75]

Figure 60: Lumefantrine

Impurities

Method

Figure 61: Desbenzyketo N-oxide

Figure 62: Monodesbutyl derivative

Figure 63: Lumefantrine N-oxide

Figure 64: Desbenzyl derivative

Figure 65: Desbenzyketo derivative

HPLC, LC-MS/MS, DAD-UV, HPLC-UV/ESI-ion trap MS

Stationary phase: puorspher STAR RP-18 end capped column

Mobile phase: 0.1 M Ammonium acetate pH 4.9: acetonitrile (10:90)

Flow rate: 2 mL/min

Injection volume: 10 μ L

Figure 66: Lumefantrine oxide

CONCLUSION:

- Impurity profiling has become the major source of the identification nowadays because of the interference of the impurity in the finished product or the prepared formulation in the pharmaceutical industry.
- Isolation and characterization of the impurities are required for the biological and pharmacological data. Therefore, some regulatory bodies and various pharmacopoeia makes impurity profiling and monitoring mandatory.
- This review provides information on the sources of impurity and their regulatory guidelines.
- It aims to provide collective data on impurity profiling done on various antimalarial drugs in the past decades.
- It also includes the impurities mentioned in the pharmacopoeias for the anti-malarial agents and their detection methods.
- Thus, overall discussion provided above about impurity profiling of anti-malarial drugs would be of broader interest to the researchers working on the related formulations.

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